

1 IMMOBILIZED HYDROXYMETHYLFURFURAL OXIDASE ENABLES ROBUST
2 BIOCATALYTIC PRODUCTION OF 2,5-FURANDICARBOXYLIC ACID FROM
3 CRUDE 5-HYDROXYMETHYLFURFURAL

4 *Darly Concha †, Garazi Ortiz-Orruño †, Marina Guillén †, Oscar Romero †, Kírian*
5 *Bonet-Ragel † **

6 † Bioprocess Engineering and Applied Biocatalysis Group, Department of Chemical,
7 Biological and Environmental Engineering, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193
8 Bellaterra, Spain.

9 **Corresponding Author**

10 *** Kírian Bonet-Ragel**

11 Department of Chemical, Biological and Environmental Engineering, Universitat
12 Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Catalonia, Spain.

13 Telephone: +34 93 581 4791

14 Kirian.bonet@uab.cat

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18 ABSTRACT

19 Bioplastics such as poly(ethylene 2,5-furandicarboxylate) (PEF), synthesized from bio-
20 based 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA), offer a promising alternative to conventional
21 petrochemical-derived plastics. The enzymatic conversion of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural
22 (HMF) to FDCA using engineered variants of hydroxymethylfurfural oxidase (HMFO)
23 represents an environmentally benign approach, as the enzyme catalyzes all three
24 oxidation steps required for FDCA synthesis.

25 This study presents an intensified biocatalytic system for the sustainable production of
26 FDCA, employing the engineered enzyme 8BxHMFO fused with a carbohydrate-binding
27 module (CBM3) and immobilized on microcrystalline cellulose (Perloza MT100) to
28 avoid oxygen interfacial inactivation. The system was first optimized using pure HMF,
29 achieving high conversion rates (>95%), a maximum FDCA yield of 7.2 g/L. Reactions
30 were performed using a crude extract rich in HMF (15% wt/wt). Despite the presence of
31 impurities, the immobilized enzyme maintained high conversion efficiency, with only a
32 30% reduction in FDCA yield compared to pure substrate. FDCA recovery was achieved
33 with 72% efficiency using a mild, ethanol-based extraction process.

34 These findings, along with an evaluation of sustainable indicators, validate the robustness
35 of the immobilized HMFO system under realistic conditions and demonstrate its potential
36 as a sustainable platform for FDCA production, contributing to the broader adoption of
37 PEF bioplastics.

38 KEYWORDS

39 Biocatalysis; 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA); 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF);
40 Enzyme immobilization; Hydroxymethylfurfural oxidase (HMFO); Cellulose-based
41 supports; Sustainable plastics.

42 HIGHLIGHTS

- 43 • One-step immobilization on renewable cellulose yields stable and cost-efficient
44 biocatalyst.
- 45 • Immobilized HMFO (CBM3-8BxHMFO) enables efficient FDCA production
46 from crude HMF extract.
- 47 • Conversion of crude HMF achieved an excellent 70.6% FDCA yield and good
48 titer (5.7 g/L).
- 49 • Sustainable and efficient mild ethanol-based downstream process recover to
50 FDCA.

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55 SYNOPSIS

56 This work demonstrates a green biocatalytic route converting lignocellulosic HMF into
57 FDCA, advancing sustainable polymer production through enzyme immobilization and
58 renewable supports.

59 1. INTRODUCTION

60 The widespread use of plastic materials, while indispensable to modern life due to their
61 durability and versatility, has generated severe environmental consequences. Among
62 them, polyethylene terephthalate (PET), a fossil-derived polymer extensively used in
63 packaging and textiles, contributes substantially to plastic pollution in terrestrial and
64 marine ecosystems (Djapovic et al., 2021; Sanders et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2021). The
65 shortcomings of current recycling technologies, which remain energetically intensive and
66 environmentally detrimental, underscore the urgency of developing sustainable
67 alternatives (Maurya et al., 2020; Ügdüler et al., 2020).

68 In response to these sustainability challenges, poly(ethylene 2,5-furandicarboxylate)
69 (PEF) has emerged as a promising bio-based alternative to PET. PEF is synthesized from
70 renewable resources and utilizes 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA) as a monomer,
71 replacing terephthalic acid in conventional polyesters. In addition to its sustainable origin,
72 PEF offers superior barrier properties and thermal stability, making it a competitive
73 bioplastic for industrial applications (Eerhart et al., 2012; Hwang et al., 2020; Kumar et
74 al., 2024).

75 FDCA can be produced via the selective oxidation of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), a
76 platform chemical obtained from lignocellulosic biomass. Traditional chemical oxidation
77 routes, such as noble metal or transition metal oxide catalysis, require harsh reaction
78 conditions, elevated temperatures, and toxic solvents, leading to undesirable byproducts
79 and high processing costs (Pei et al., 2023; Sajid et al., 2018; Totaro et al., 2022). Recent
80 advances using heterogeneous catalysts, including Co-based oxides or microwave-
81 assisted noble metal systems, have improved activity and energy efficiency but still rely
82 on chemical oxidants and pressurized conditions (Liu et al., 2020; Ji et al., 2018; Peng et
83 al., 2025). In contrast, enzymatic oxidation offers an environmentally benign alternative,

84 operating under mild conditions, employing molecular oxygen as a clean oxidant, and
85 delivering high selectivity toward FDCA (Meyer et al., 2022; Troiano et al., 2020).

86 Enzymatic oxidation of HMF frequently relies on multi-enzymatic cascades, which
87 complicates process optimization. Nevertheless, hydroxymethylfurfural oxidase
88 (HMFO), a flavoprotein oxidoreductase belonging to the glucose-methanol-choline
89 (GMC) enzyme superfamily, exhibits notable substrate promiscuity, catalyzing the
90 oxidation of a broad range of furanic compounds, including the primary alcohol oxidation
91 of HMF (Dijkman et al., 2015; Dijkman and Fraaije, 2014). These enzymes contain flavin
92 adenine dinucleotide (FAD) as a tightly bound prosthetic group, which is essential for
93 their redox activity (Dijkman and Fraaije, 2014; Viñambres et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2021).

94 Native HMFOs, such as those from *Methylovorus sp.* MP688, demonstrate high catalytic
95 efficiency in oxidizing both alcohol and aldehyde functional groups (Dijkman and
96 Fraaije, 2014; Viñambres et al., 2020). The enzyme catalyzes the full oxidation of HMF
97 to FDCA through a sequential three-step process that includes the formation of
98 intermediate compounds: 2,5-diformylfuran (DFF) and 5-formylfuran-2-carboxylic acid
99 (FFCA).

100 Advances in protein engineering have enabled the development of improved HMFO
101 variants, such as 8BxHMFO, capable of catalyzing complete oxidation of HMF into
102 FDCA, exhibiting enhanced thermal stability and reduced susceptibility to oxidative
103 deactivation position them as promising candidates for industrial-scale biocatalytic
104 applications (Martin et al., 2018; Sánchez-Ruiz et al., 2021). Nevertheless, their practical
105 implementation is still hampered by challenges such as poor stability at gas-liquid
106 interfaces, product inhibition, particularly associated with hydrogen peroxide
107 accumulation, and low expression yields in recombinant hosts (Dijkman and Fraaije,
108 2014; Høst et al., 2025; Sánchez-Ruiz et al., 2021). To overcome these limitations, recent

109 efforts have focused on rational enzyme design and fine-tuning of reaction parameters to
110 enhance overall catalytic efficiency and robustness (Wu et al., 2021).

111 However, HMFOs still faces challenges in operational stability due to their oxidative
112 mechanism. The use of molecular oxygen as an electron acceptor leads to local oxygen
113 depletion and the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which may induce enzyme
114 deactivation. Furthermore, the gas-liquid interface in aerated bioreactors promotes
115 protein denaturation via interfacial adsorption and aggregation (Høst et al., 2025; Wang
116 et al., 2023). To overcome these limitations, enzyme immobilization has been widely
117 adopted as a strategy to improve catalytic stability, enable enzyme reuse, and facilitate
118 integration into continuous processes (Maghraby et al., 2023; Ndochinwa et al., 2024).
119 Enzyme immobilization is a well-established technique that improves catalytic stability,
120 enhances resistance to denaturation, and enables application in multi-enzyme cascade
121 systems (Robescu and Bavaro, 2025). Additionally, immobilization facilitates enzyme
122 recovery and reuse, offering a cost-effective and sustainable solution (Maghraby et al.,
123 2023).

124 In particular, immobilization via carbohydrate-binding modules (CBMs) offers a
125 sustainable and efficient platform. This approach aligns with the principles of green
126 chemistry by enabling enzyme purification and immobilization in a single step using
127 renewable supports such as microcrystalline cellulose. CBM3 from *Clostridium*
128 *thermocellum* binds specifically to crystalline cellulose and allows site-directed
129 immobilization (Benito et al., 2022; Oliveira et al., 2015). It also allows one-step
130 purification and immobilization through specific carbohydrate interactions, providing a
131 sustainable and cost-efficient alternative to traditional immobilization based on chemical
132 functionalization (Benito et al., 2022; Roberts et al., 2021).

133 Despite these developments underscore the increasing relevance of HMFOs in industrial
134 biotechnology, playing a central role in advancing sustainable polymer production
135 (Herlina et al., 2023; Sánchez-Ruiz et al., 2021; Viñambres et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2020).
136 Most biocatalytic studies for FDCA production have employed pure HMF as the
137 substrate, which does not reflect the complexity of real biomass-derived hydrolysates.
138 Crude HMF streams often contain impurities such as humins, organic acids, and residual
139 sugars that may inhibit enzyme activity or interfere with downstream processing
140 (Birmingham et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2024). Therefore, it is essential to validate the
141 performance of immobilized biocatalysts under these more industrial/biorefinery relevant
142 conditions to ensure their feasibility for industrial implementation.

143 In this study, we report the expression of the engineered 8BxHMFO enzyme fused to
144 CBM3, its immobilization on a microcrystalline cellulose supports, and its application in
145 the biocatalytic production of FDCA. To enhance enzyme stability, the immobilized
146 biocatalyst was further crosslinked with glutaraldehyde. The catalytic performance was
147 evaluated using both pure HMF and crude HMF. This work applied an intensification
148 strategy, in which multiple HMF concentrations were tested. The results contribute to the
149 integration of biocatalytic systems into circular biorefinery schemes for bio-based
150 polymer manufacturing, highlighting the system's adaptability to realistic feedstocks and
151 alignment with sustainability goals.

152 2. METHODS

153 2.1. Materials

154 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), 2,5-diformylfuran (DFF), 5-formyl-2-furancarboxylic
155 acid (FFCA), and 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA) were purchased from TCI
156 Chemicals (Japan). 25 – 35% 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural (Crude HMF) was obtained from
157 AVA Biochem (Switzerland). Flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD) was obtained from

158 Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Microcrystalline cellulose Perloza MT100 was
159 provided by Perloza s.r.o. (Czech Republic). Avicel® PH-200 microcrystalline cellulose
160 sample was kindly donated by DuPont™ N&B (New York, NY, USA).

161 2.2.Enzymes

162 An octuple mutant variant of HMF oxidase (8BxHMFO; I73V, H74Y, G356K, V367R,
163 T414K, A419Y, A435E, and W466F) from *Methylovorus sp.* was genetically fused to a
164 type 3 cellulose-binding module (CBM3) from *Clostridium thermocellum*. The synthetic
165 gene was obtained from GenScript (USA) and cloned into the pVEF expression vector.
166 The fusion enzyme was expressed in an auxotrophic M15-derived *Escherichia coli strain*,
167 cultivated in high cell density cultures in fed-batch reactor using an antibiotic-free defined
168 medium (Vidal et al., 2008). Cell disruption was performed at 1.6 kbar using high-
169 pressure disruptor (Constant Systems cell disruptor), and the enzyme was recovered in
170 the soluble fraction of the lysate, yielding a specific activity of $14.8 \pm 0.7 \text{ U} \cdot \text{gDCW}^{-1}$, a
171 volumetric activity of $1209.5 \pm 59.3 \text{ U} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, and an enzyme concentration of $2762.3 \pm$
172 $126.5 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$. This corresponded a specific activity of $0.44 \pm 0.03 \text{ U} \cdot \text{mg}^{-1}$. Catalase was
173 purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA) and used as auxiliary enzyme.

174 2.3.HMFO Activity assay

175 The oxidase activity of CBM3-8BxHMFO was measured by monitoring oxygen
176 consumption using a Pyro Science robust oxygen probe coupled to a FireSting-PRO
177 oxygen meter. Reactions were performed in 2.5 mL of 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0)
178 at 30 °C with 300 rpm agitation. Enzymatic reactions were initiated by adding the enzyme
179 (soluble and immobilized) and 60 mM HMF. One unit of enzymatic activity was defined
180 as the amount of enzyme required to consume 1 μmol of molecular oxygen per minute
181 under these conditions.

182 2.4. One step purification and immobilization of CBM3-8BxHMFO

183 One step purification and immobilization procedure was carried out by incubating 9 mL
184 of lysate containing CBM3-8BxHMFO with 1 g Perloza MT100 or Avicel PH200 at
185 room temperature under gentle rotation using a roller mixer for 30 min. Enzyme loading
186 varied among 0.65 and 4 U per gram of support. The immobilized enzyme was washed
187 with 1:20 solid-to-liquid ratio of 50 mM Tris -HCl buffer pH 8 and recovered by vacuum
188 filtration.

189 A post-immobilization treatment was applied to the immobilized biocatalyst using
190 different concentration of glutaraldehyde solutions ranging from 0.1% to 1% (v/v) in 50
191 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0), using a 1:10 solid-to-liquid ratio. The suspension was
192 incubated for 30 min. under gentle agitation, followed by filtration and extensive washing
193 with the same buffer. The resulting crosslinked enzyme derivative was stored at 4 °C until
194 further use.

195 Immobilization was evaluated by determining the immobilization yield (IY%), recovery
196 of catalytic activity (RCA%), retained activity (RA%), protein immobilization yield
197 (protein %), and protein loading (mg/g_{support}) (Benito et al., 2022).

198 Immobilization yield (IY%): $\left(\frac{A_i - A_{sn}}{A_i}\right) \times 100$ (Equation 1)

199 Recovery activity (RCA%): $\left(\frac{Ad * g_{support}}{A_i * blank\ volume\ (mL)}\right) \times 100$ (Equation 2)

200 Retained activity (RA%): $\left(\frac{A_{sus}}{A_i - A_{sn}}\right) \times 100$ (Equation 3)

201 Immobilization yield (protein %): $\left(\frac{P_i - P_{sn}}{P_i}\right) \times 100$ (Equation 4)

202 Immobilized protein per g support: $\left(\frac{P_i - P_{sn}}{g_{support}}\right)$ (Equation 5)

203 Purification factor: $\left(\frac{E_{support} (mg \cdot mL^{-1})}{E_{offered} (mg \cdot mL^{-1})}\right)$ (Equation 6)

204 Where, A_i : initial enzyme activity offered; A_{sn} : the remaining enzyme activity measured
205 in the supernatant at the end of the experiment; A_{sus} : the enzyme activity of the
206 suspension measured at the end of the experiment; A_d : the enzyme activity of the
207 derivative obtained at the end of the experiment; P_i : the initial protein concentration; P_{sn} :
208 the supernatant protein concentration (unbound proteins); $E_{support}$: concentration of
209 enzyme immobilized on the support; $E_{offered}$: concentration of enzyme offered, from the
210 lysate.

211 2.5. Protein concentration

212 Protein concentration in soluble and immobilized fractions was quantified using the
213 Bradford assay (Coomassie® Protein Assay Reagent Kit). Briefly, 7 μ L of sample was
214 mixed with 200 μ L of reagent and incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes.
215 Absorbance was recorded at 595 nm using a spectrophotometer. A bovine serum albumin
216 (BSA) calibration curve ranging from 0 to 2 mg/mL was used as a standard.

217 2.6. Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy

218 The immobilized CBM3-8BxHMFO enzyme on microcrystalline cellulose (Perloza MT
219 100) was analyzed by fluorescence confocal microscopy. No external fluorescent labeling
220 was required, since the FAD cofactor of HMFO exhibits intrinsic autofluorescence. A
221 suspension of the enzyme-functionalized particles was prepared in 50 mM Tris-HCl
222 buffer (pH 8.0), diluted (1:100). Samples were examined using a Zeiss LSM confocal
223 microscope with excitation at 405 nm and emission collection between 408–551 nm,
224 corresponding to the autofluorescence spectrum of FAD. Confocal images were initially

225 processed using ImageJ (FIJI), and further visualization and analysis were carried out
226 with Imaris Viewer (version 10.2.0).

227 2.7. Thermostability analysis

228 Thermal stability of the soluble and immobilized enzymes was evaluated by determining
229 the melting temperature (T_m) using SYPRO Orange dye. Samples (22.5 μL) were mixed
230 with 2.5 μL of SYPRO dye in a 96-well plate. The melt curve was recorded from 10 $^\circ\text{C}$
231 to 95 $^\circ\text{C}$ in 0.5 $^\circ\text{C}$ increments using the CFX96 Touch Real-Time PCR Detection System
232 (Bio-Rad Laboratories), with fluorescence measurements acquired at each temperature
233 interval.

234 2.8. FDCA production using immobilized CBM3-8BxHMFO

235 The oxidation of HMF was conducted in a basket-type bioreactor using immobilized
236 CBM3-8BxHMFO. The reactions were performed using the enzyme derivative that had
237 been previously immobilized on Perloza MT100 and cross-linked with 0.25%
238 glutaraldehyde, resulting in a protein loading of approximately 50 mg per gram of
239 support. Reactions were carried out in 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0) containing various
240 concentrations of HMF (6–125 mM), catalase (97.7 $\text{U}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$), and continuous air bubbling
241 at a flow rate of 0.6 vvm. Temperature and agitation were maintained at 30 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 300
242 rpm, respectively. pH was monitored and controlled using 1.5 M NaOH and a Metrohm
243 916 Ti-Touch titrator. Samples were withdrawn at defined time intervals and analyzed
244 via HPLC.

245 2.9. HPLC analysis

246 Quantification of HMF and its oxidation products (FDCA, DFF, and FFCA) was
247 performed using 1220 Infinity Agilent HPLC system equipped with a 1260 Infinity II
248 Agilent UV detector. Separation was achieved with a SUPELCOGEL C-610H column

249 using 5 mM H₂SO₄ as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min and 30 °C column
250 temperature. Detection was carried out at 264 nm (Sánchez-Ruiz et al., 2021). The
251 retention times for each compound were 51.3 min for HMF, 64.6 min for DFF, 37.4 min
252 for FFCA, and 26.2 min for FDCA.

253 2.10. FDCA Purification

254 FDCA purification was performed by acid-induced precipitation followed by sequential
255 washing and solvent extraction. Following the biocatalytic reactions, hydrochloric acid
256 was added dropwise to the reaction mixture until the pH reached 0, promoting complete
257 precipitation of FDCA. The resulting precipitate was collected by vacuum filtration and
258 initially washed with 100 mM HCl to remove soluble impurities. The solid was
259 subsequently subjected to three additional washes with acidified water to ensure the
260 removal of residual salts and unreacted substrates.

261 To enhance purity, the FDCA precipitate was dissolved into three volumes of ethanol
262 under agitation, and the resulting suspension was filtered to eliminate ethanol-insoluble
263 impurities. The ethanol phase containing FDCA was then concentrated by rotary
264 evaporation at 40 °C until dryness. The final solid product was stored at room temperature
265 until further analysis. The purification workflow is summarized in Figure S7.

266 2.11. Sustainable indicators

267 The E-factor and Global Warming Potential (GWP) were utilized as indicators of
268 environmental sustainability. Equations and calculations are described in the
269 Supplementary Information. Briefly, the E-factor is a direct indication of the amount of
270 waste generated by the process per unit of the product of interest. GWP is a metric that
271 quantifies the total amount of CO₂ emitted by a process per kilogram of product. This
272 metric may be calculated in two ways. Firstly, it may be calculated as GWP_{energy}, which

273 is the GWP that results from the energy used in the reaction. Secondly, it may be
274 calculated as the GWP_{mass} , which is the GWP that results from the resources consumed
275 and disposed of during the process (Domínguez de María, 2024).

276 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

277 3.1. ENZYME IMMOBILIZATION ON MICROCRYSTALLINE CELLULOSE.

278 FDCA synthesis using soluble 8BxHMFO soluble, with air bubbling to supply molecular
279 oxygen, led to rapid enzyme inactivation with the enzyme retaining 20% of its initial
280 activity after 52 hours (Figure S1). While bubbling air into the reaction medium is a
281 common strategy for oxygen supply, it is well documented that interfacial stress at the
282 gas - liquid interface can lead to enzyme denaturation (Betancor et al., 2004), a
283 phenomenon also observed for HMFO (Høst et al., 2025). This phenomenon, attributed
284 to unfolding, aggregation, and loss of enzymatic activity, is primarily caused by dynamic
285 gas-liquid interfaces and mechanical agitation (Wang et al., 2023). These findings
286 underscore the importance of enzyme stabilization strategies, such as immobilization,
287 especially for applications involving gaseous substrates. Immobilization can provide a
288 protective microenvironment that shields the enzyme from interfacial stresses at gas-
289 liquid boundaries, thereby reducing the risk of denaturation and maintaining catalytic
290 activity over prolonged reaction times.

291 To enable an efficient, cost-effective, and sustainable immobilization strategy, the
292 enzyme 8BxHMFO was genetically fused with CBM3, a carbohydrate-binding module
293 known for its strong affinity toward cellulose. This fusion facilitated a one-step
294 purification and immobilization process onto microcrystalline cellulose, an attractive
295 support material due to its cost-effectiveness, renewability, and sustainability. Two
296 different types of microcrystalline cellulose supports were evaluated: Avicel® PH-200,
297 characterized by its irregular particle morphology, porosity, and high crystallinity, and

298 Perloza MT100, which presents a uniform spherical structure of porous regenerated
299 cellulose gel.

300 The immobilization process was completed within 30 minutes in both cases, as confirmed
301 by the complete absence of enzymatic activity in the supernatant (Figure 1A; Figure S2),
302 indicating full adsorption of the enzyme onto the support (Perloza MT100). SDS-PAGE
303 analysis (Figure 1B) corroborated the efficient enrichment of the target protein. Lane 2
304 corresponds to the total cell lysate, while Lane 3 represents the immobilized enzyme on
305 Avicel® PH-200, showing a prominent band consistent with the expected molecular
306 weight of CBM3-8BxHMFO. Similarly, lanes 4 and 5 represent the lysate and
307 immobilized enzyme on Perloza MT100, respectively, both confirming successful
308 immobilization through the appearance of the target protein band. The strategy achieved
309 a purification factor of 22.5 for Avicel® PH-200 and 19.8 for Perloza MT100,
310 underscoring the efficiency of CBM3-mediated immobilization as a one-step strategy for
311 purification and immobilization. These values reflect a highly efficient capture of the
312 target enzyme from crude lysates and validate the use of CBMs as functional affinity tags
313 for biocatalyst preparation. Comparable findings have been reported in previous studies
314 employing CBM fusions. Ramón-Luing et al. (2006) demonstrated full recovery and
315 immobilization of GroEL-CBD onto microcrystalline cellulose directly from cell lysate,
316 emphasizing the cost-efficiency of this method. Gennari et al. (2022) and Qin et al. (2019)
317 also highlighted the capacity of CBM-tagged enzymes to bind selectively to cellulosic
318 matrices, enabling enzyme recovery without prior purification. Furthermore, Benito et al.
319 (2022) reported purification factors between 3 and 10.1 for CBM-tagged alcohol
320 dehydrogenases. Altogether, these results confirm that CBM-based immobilization is not
321 only technically robust but also strategically advantageous, as it integrates purification
322 and immobilization, thereby significantly reducing downstream processing costs, which

323 can constitute 50-80% of total manufacturing expenses (Barbosa et al., 2015; Boodhoo et
324 al., 2022; Rathore and Kapoor, 2015).

325

326 Figure 1: A) Immobilization kinetics of CBM3-8BxHMFO in Perloza MT100 Support.
327 B) SDS-PAGE: lanes 1 and 6 MWM (kDa); (CBM3-8BxHMFO, MW: 75.1 kDa) lanes
328 2 and 4: blank and immobilized enzyme onto Avicel® PH-200; lanes 4 and 5: blank and
329 immobilized enzyme onto Perloza MT100.

330 Table S1 summarizes key performance indicators of one step purification immobilization
331 process. A high immobilization yield and recovery activity of 72% and 16% was obtained
332 for Avicel® PH-20, and 98% and 10% for Perloza MT100, respectively. Both supports
333 exhibited a high protein loading capacity of 50 mg per gram of support. These outcomes
334 are consistent with previous reports employing various microcrystalline cellulose
335 matrices such as Avicel® PH-101, regenerated amorphous cellulose (RAC), and bacterial
336 nanocellulose which have demonstrated similar or slightly lower adsorption capacities
337 (Benito et al., 2022; Li et al., 2025; Qin et al., 2019; Ramón-Luing et al., 2006). The high
338 immobilization efficiency and rapid binding kinetics observed in this study support the
339 effectiveness of CBM3-based affinity immobilization as a robust, one-step purification
340 strategy. The low-cost process and renewable nature of the support highlight its industrial

341 relevance, particularly in the context of sustainable biocatalyst design. Such an approach
342 directly aligns with the principles of circular economy, leveraging low-cost agro-
343 industrial residues and enhancing the environmental sustainability of bioprocesses
344 (Benito et al., 2022; Oliveira et al., 2015).

345 First attempt of FDCA production using immobilized CBM3-8BxHMFO showed a
346 progressive loss of enzyme activity (Figure S3). This phenomenon was attributed to the
347 desorption of the enzyme from the cellulose matrix, which released the enzyme into the
348 solution where it was likely denatured (Figure S4 and Table S2). This outcome is
349 consistent with recent studies demonstrating that CBM-cellulose interactions, particularly
350 those involving CBM3, are dynamic and reversible, with possible elution in the presence
351 of glucose or low-polarity solvents (Liu et al., 2022; Oliveira et al., 2015).

352 To improve retention and enhance operational stability, glutaraldehyde was employed as
353 cross-linking agent. This bifunctional reagent can form covalent bonds between enzyme
354 molecules. Its effectiveness in stabilizing immobilized enzymes by reinforcing their
355 structural conformation is well supported in the literature (Mateo et al., 2007; Sheldon
356 and van Pelt, 2013)

357 Figure 2A shows that cross-linking with glutaraldehyde 0.25% resulted in a moderate
358 reduction in recovered enzymatic activity to 20%. This decrease suggests partial
359 restriction of enzyme flexibility, possibly impairing substrate access to the active site.
360 Notably, in the absence of glutaraldehyde, only 30% of the initial activity was recovered,
361 which can be attributed to the high protein loading on the support estimated at nearly 50
362 mg protein per gram of support. Such high surface occupancy may promote a hinder
363 substrate diffusion, leading to limited catalytic performance (Arana-Peña et al., 2020). At
364 higher concentrations (1%), catalytic activity was almost complete reduced, indicating
365 that excessive cross-linking severely hinders enzymatic activity.

366 SDS-PAGE analysis of the cross-linked derivatives (Figure 2B) confirmed enhanced
367 enzyme retention on the support, as demonstrated by the progressive disappearance of the
368 soluble enzyme band with increasing glutaraldehyde concentration. This pattern reflects
369 stronger covalent bonding between the enzyme and among enzyme molecules, improving
370 immobilization stability. However, this enhanced retention came at the cost of catalytic
371 performance. At 0.25% glutaraldehyde, recovered enzymatic activity dropped to 20%,
372 suggesting a trade-off between retention and catalytic functionality. Notably, high
373 concentrations of glutaraldehyde (e.g., 1%) resulted in near-complete inactivation,
374 consistent with previous reports describing enzyme deactivation due to excessive cross-
375 linking (Liu et al., 2024; Modenez et al., 2018; Perzon et al., 2017; Xu et al., 2018). While
376 low glutaraldehyde concentrations have been shown to preserve catalytic function and
377 reduce leaching (Liu et al., 2024; Modenez et al., 2018), the 0.25% cross-linked derivative
378 was selected for subsequent experiments as the most balanced condition, providing
379 improved retention while maintaining acceptable activity.

380

381 Figure 2: A) Recovery activity of the different concentrations of glutaraldehyde used as
382 crosslinker. B) SDS-PAGE gel of immobilization fractions with different glutaraldehyde
383 concentration, where lane 1 is the molecular weight marker in kDa; (CBM3-8BxHMFO,

384 MW = 75.1 kDa). Lanes 2 to 6 show the immobilized derivative with 0, 0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 1
385 % glutaraldehyde respectively.

386 3.2.CHARACTERIZATION OF IMMOBILIZED DERIVATIVES: THERMAL 387 STABILITY AND MICROSCOPIC DISTRIBUTION

388 To evaluate the impact of immobilization and cross-linking on the structural stability of
389 CBM3-8BxHMFO, the melting temperature (T_m) was measured for the soluble enzyme,
390 its immobilized form, and the glutaraldehyde cross-linked derivatives (Table S3). The
391 immobilized enzyme exhibited a T_m of 53.2°C, which represents a significant increase
392 from the T_m of the soluble counterpart (49.7°C). This enhancement in thermal stability is
393 likely attributable to the conformational restrictions imposed by the covalent and non-
394 covalent interactions with the cellulose matrix, which can limit the flexibility of the
395 polypeptide chain and reduce the likelihood of thermal unfolding (Ariaeenejad and
396 Motamedi, 2025; Rodrigues et al., 2021; Shen et al., 2024). Such stabilization has been
397 widely observed for immobilized enzymes and is particularly relevant for biocatalytic
398 applications requiring elevated operational temperatures. The observed increase in T_m
399 further supports the role of immobilization not only in facilitating enzyme reuse but also
400 in enhancing resistance to thermal denaturation, a desirable trait for long-term processing
401 under industrial conditions.

402 Conversely, increasing the concentration of glutaraldehyde beyond the optimal range led
403 to a slight but consistent decrease in T_m values. This observation, consistent with
404 previously reports, suggests that excessive cross-linking can introduce localized structural
405 stresses or distortions, disrupting the optimal enzyme conformations required for thermal
406 resilience (Barbosa et al., 2014; López-Gallego et al., 2005). In contrast, variations in
407 enzyme loading, even at high immobilization densities (51.9 mg·g⁻¹_{support}), did not lead to
408 measurable effects on thermal stability within the tested range. This indicates that the

409 conformational stabilization conferred by the support matrix predominates over potential
410 crowding effects (Ariaeenejad and Motamedi, 2025), at least within the conditions
411 evaluated.

412 To gain detailed spatial insights into the localization and distribution of the immobilized
413 enzyme within the microcrystalline cellulose matrix, confocal fluorescence microscopy
414 was carried out. Leveraging the intrinsic fluorescence of the FAD cofactor in 8BxHMFO,
415 visualization was achieved without the need for external labelling, preserving the native
416 structure of the biocatalyst. Multiplanar imaging revealed a uniform and homogeneous
417 distribution of the enzyme throughout the porous structure of the microcrystalline
418 cellulose particles, as observed in different focal planes (Figure 3). This spatial uniformity
419 confirms effective diffusion and attachment of the enzyme across the full depth of the
420 support, which is a desirable feature for heterogeneous catalysis. Such even spatial
421 distribution facilitates consistent substrate accessibility across the matrix and minimizes
422 diffusional gradients, which can otherwise limit reaction efficiency in packed-bed or
423 batch systems (Diamanti and López-Gallego, 2024; Santiago-Arcos et al., 2023).
424 Moreover, this structural uniformity is expected to enhance the operational stability of
425 the system by preventing localized enzyme overloading and associated mass transfer
426 limitations (Bolivar and López-Gallego, 2020).

427

428 Figure 3: Confocal fluorescence images of three different focal planes of the CBM3-
429 8BxHMFO in Perloza MT100 Support.

430 3.3. INTENSIFICATION OF ENZYMATIC FDCA PRODUCTION USING PURE 431 HMF

432 To assess the catalytic performance of the immobilized CBM3-8BxHMFO system, batch
433 reactions were carried out using varying concentrations of pure HMF as substrate. The
434 reactions were conducted in a 20 mL basket reactor, which maintained a constant air
435 supply $12 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ (0.6 vvm), temperature 30°C , and pH 8, scheme of the reaction
436 system is shown in Figure S5. This evaluation aimed to determine the optimal conditions
437 for conversion to FDCA, while simultaneously quantifying the accumulation of reaction
438 intermediates and assessing system productivity.

439 The enzymatic oxidation of HMF to FDCA was studied under a range of substrate
440 concentrations. Figure 4 focuses on the enzymatic reaction of CBM3-8BxHMFO
441 immobilized on Perloza with pure HMF. It includes the reaction profiles with (A) 6 mM,
442 (B) 12 mM, (C) 24 mM, (D) 50 mM, and (E) 125 mM HMF, as well as (F) the key process
443 metrics (conversion, yield, productivity, and FDCA titer) obtained from these reactions.

444 HMF was rapidly consumed under all tested conditions, and no significant accumulation
 445 of intermediates was observed, except in the reaction conducted at 125 mM HMF, where
 446 a notable accumulation occurred. In this case, DFF accumulated to approximately 50 mM
 447 and persisted throughout the process, indicating inefficient oxidation. Additionally,
 448 FFCA, a known potent inhibitor of 8BxHMFO (Sánchez-Ruiz et al., 2021) also
 449 accumulated significantly, reaching concentrations of about 37 mM after 72 hours. This
 450 accumulation of FFCA correlated directly with the lower FDCA yields observed in this
 451 reaction compared to those with lower HMF concentrations, which showed negligible
 452 intermediate accumulation and achieved near complete FDCA yields. It is also important
 453 to note that reaction time increased proportionally with substrate concentration, further
 454 influencing productivity at higher HMF levels.

455

456 Figure 4. Enzymatic reaction of CBM3-8BxHMFO immobilized on Perloza with pure
 457 HMF at 30 °C, pH 8, 500 rpm, 0.6 vvm air bubbling, and catalase (97.7 U mL⁻¹) at
 458 different substrate concentrations. Reactions with (A) 6 mM, (B) 12 mM, (C) 24 mM, (D)
 459 50 mM, and (E) 125 mM HMF. (F) Key process metrics of the enzymatic reactions

460 (conversion, yield, productivity, and FDCA titer) obtained with pure HMF at 6, 12, 24,
461 50, and 125 mM.

462 From the reactions carried out at different HMF concentrations, key process metrics such
463 as conversion, yield, and space-time yield (STY) were calculated to identify optimal
464 conditions. The results, summarized in Figure 4 F, show that high conversion rates were
465 consistently achieved across all tested concentrations. FDCA yield increased
466 progressively with substrate concentration up to 50 mM, beyond which no significant
467 improvement was observed. In contrast, productivity peaked at 12 mM and showed a
468 slight decline at 24 and 50 mM, with a marked decrease observed for the reaction
469 performed at 125 mM HMF. This behavior is directly related to reaction time, as substrate
470 concentration increases, longer reaction times are required, affecting the productivity.
471 Finally, the total amount of FDCA produced ($\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) increased proportionally with the
472 substrate concentration, as expected from the direct relationship with yield, reaching a
473 maximum FDCA titer in the 50 mM reaction.

474 This behaviour is consistent with the accumulation of inhibitory intermediates such as
475 FFCA at high HMF concentrations, particularly in the case of the reaction performed at
476 125 mM HMF, which can adversely affect enzymatic turnover (Sánchez-Ruiz et al.,
477 2021). Among the evaluated conditions, the reaction with 50 mM HMF provided the
478 highest FDCA titer ($7.2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), representing the best compromise between high yield and
479 productivity. This performance is notably higher than most enzymatic systems reported
480 to date, which typically reach $\leq 2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ FDCA under substrate loadings of 1.5–10 mM
481 HMF using wild-type HMFO or its early variants (Dijkman and Fraaije, 2014; Sánchez-
482 Ruiz et al., 2021; Viñambres et al., 2020). Even engineered enzymes such as 8BxHMFO
483 generally yielded $< 2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ under similar conditions (Sánchez-Ruiz et al., 2021), while
484 more recent cascades such as BpLac/CglAlcOx achieved only $\sim 0.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ FDCA at 5 mM

485 HMF (Yang et al., 2023). Only very recent advances with alternative enzymes, such as
486 the evolved PedH variant, have approached comparable levels, reaching $\sim 6 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ from 40
487 mM HMF (Liu et al., 2025).

488 3.4.EVALUATION OF IMMOBILIZED BIOCATALYTS UNDER RELEVANT 489 INDUSTRIAL/BIOREFINERY CONDITIONS.

490 To evaluate the system's applicability under real biorefinery, the reaction was performed
491 using a crude substrate extract containing 15% wt/wt of HMF. The reaction was carried
492 out at a 50 mM HMF concentration, a condition that corresponds to the highest titer using
493 pure HMF. As shown in Figure 5, substrate conversion was nearly complete. DFF levels
494 increased initially but were depleted after 73 hours, while FFCA remained at sub-
495 inhibitory concentrations. The FDCA production profile showed a sustained increase
496 throughout the process, indicating that the immobilized enzyme remained functionally
497 active even in the presence of potential impurities present in the crude feedstock.

498

499 Figure 5. Enzymatic reaction of CBM3-8BxHMFO immobilized on Perloza with 51 mM
500 crude HMF at 30 °C, pH 8, 500 rpm, 0.6 vvm air bubbling and catalase ($97.7 \text{ U}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$).

501 A comparison between reactions using pure and crude HMF is presented in Table 1. The
502 immobilized CBM3-8BxHMFO efficiently oxidized pure HMF, achieving 99.7%
503 conversion with a 91.3% yield, corresponding to 7.2 g·L⁻¹ FDCA and a space-time yield
504 (STY) of 89 mg·L⁻¹·h⁻¹ in 81 h. When crude HMF was used under the same conditions,
505 the conversion remained high (98.7%), but the yield dropped to 70.6%, resulting in 5.7
506 g·L⁻¹ FDCA and a lower STY of 57 mg·L⁻¹·h⁻¹ over 100 h.

507 This decline is likely attributable to the presence of inhibitory compounds such as furfural
508 derivatives, phenolics, or residual sugars commonly found in non-purified lignocellulosic
509 hydrolysates (Wang et al., 2024). These components may interfere with enzymatic
510 turnover or destabilize the biocatalyst over prolonged reaction times. In the present study,
511 a characterization of the crude extract was performed (Figure S6), and no compounds of
512 this nature could be identified, even though non-identified impurities or by-products were
513 detected which may act as enzyme inhibitors. Nonetheless, the enzyme's ability to sustain
514 FDCA formation in such a complex matrix highlights its robustness and supports its
515 practical application in the context of biorefinery integration and circular economy
516 strategies. To our knowledge, no reports using enzymes (soluble or immobilized) have
517 previously described the production of FDCA from crude HMF. However, Birmingham
518 et al. (2021) demonstrated that even the partial oxidation of crude HMF to DFF required
519 extensive enzyme engineering (GOase variants) and biphasic systems to maintain high
520 conversion at 100 g·L⁻¹. Similarly, Milić et al. (2023) reviewed patents (Rode et al., 2021)
521 reporting low FDCA titers (20–50 mM) when *Pseudomonas* M11 resting cells processed
522 crude lignocellulosic extracts containing residual HMF, while only 66% yield was
523 achieved with *Klebsiella oxytoca* MCC0144 using HMF extracted from fructose. These
524 examples highlight that unrefined feedstocks strongly reduce both yield and achievable
525 product titters. In comparison, the immobilized CBM3-8BxHMFO maintains high

526 conversion and interesting FDCA titers even with crude HMF, outperforming whole-cell
527 systems described in patents, which typically operate at only 20–50 mM HMF and yield
528 20–50 mM FDCA, or reach conversions of ~66% after 36 h, and often require 50–100 h
529 of reaction to achieve incomplete product formation (Milić et al., 2023). Nonetheless, the
530 gap between pure and crude HMF indicates that further process optimization could
531 enhance robustness against complex feedstocks and improve productivity. Importantly,
532 our results demonstrate that the immobilized CBM3-8BxHMFO is capable of sustaining
533 FDCA production from minimally processed substrates, underscoring the robustness of
534 this biocatalyst and its adaptability to realistic biorefinery streams. These findings
535 strongly support the technical feasibility of integrating this enzymatic platform into waste
536 valorization schemes.

537 Table 1. Main results of enzymatic reactions with immobilized CBM3-8BxHMFO at 30
538 °C, pH 8, and air bubbling, using crude HMF compared with reactions performed under
539 similar conditions with pure HMF.

HMF	HMF (mM)	Time (h)	Conversion (%)	Yield (%)	FDCA (g·L ⁻¹)	STY (mg·L ⁻¹ ·h ⁻¹)
Pure	50.6	81	99.7	91.3	7.2	89
Crude	51.5	100	98.7	70.6	5.7	57

540

541 3.5.FDCA PURIFICATION AND RECOVERY.

542 Finally, in the case of enzymatic FDCA production from crude HMF, a purification
543 process was implemented to isolate and recover the target compound. This step was
544 critical for confirming the feasibility of integrating the biocatalytic platform into real-
545 world applications, particularly in the production of bio-based monomers from renewable

546 resources. A scheme of the purification process is shown in Figure S7. Initially, the
547 immobilized enzyme was removed by filtration, and the FDCA present in the crude
548 reaction mixture was subsequently purified by acid precipitation, washing, redissolution
549 in ethanol, and ethanol removal by distillation. The purified FDCA powder was weighed
550 and dissolved to be analyzed by HPLC. The analysis indicated a purity of approximately
551 88%, validating the effectiveness of the recovery process but suggesting minor
552 optimization is needed to reach maximum purity..

553 As presented in Table S4, the purification strategy allowed for the extraction of 72% of
554 the total FDCA into an ethanol-soluble fraction. This high extraction efficiency
555 underscores the environmental compatibility of the process. These results confirm the
556 scalability and technical simplicity of the recovery workflow, while supporting its
557 alignment with sustainable processing standards.

558 The successful isolation of FDCA from crude lignocellulosic feedstock, coupled with
559 high conversion rates and resilience to impurities demonstrated in the previous section,
560 provides a strong foundation for downstream valorization. These findings reinforce the
561 viability of deploying immobilized oxidases in biorefineries aimed at upgrading biomass-
562 derived intermediates into high-value monomers for the sustainable polymer industry.

563 3.6.GREEN METRICS OF THE BIOPROCESS.

564 In the context of a carbon-constrained economy, quantifying the environmental impact of
565 chemical and biocatalytic processes is essential to move beyond qualitative claims of
566 “greenness”. Consequently, the E-factor and the global warming potential (GWP) for this
567 study were determined based on the approach previously reported by (Domínguez De
568 María, 2024).

569 As previously mentioned, no reports using isolated enzymes have described the
 570 production of FDCA directly from crude HMF. Therefore, the comparison of these gate-
 571 to-gate green metrics for crude-HMF-based FDCA focuses primarily on
 572 biotransformations using whole-cell systems. The results, presented in Table 2,
 573 demonstrate that the enzymatic process developed in this study is substantially more
 574 sustainable than previously reported routes. The data used for determining these metrics
 575 is summarized in Table S.5.

576 Table 2. Green metrics values obtained from environmental performance evaluation for
 577 some studies and the present one.

E-factor	GWP (mass)	GWP (energy)	Reference
	kg CO ₂ -eq·kg ⁻¹ _{FDCA}	kg CO ₂ -eq·kg ⁻¹ _{FDCA}	
782.7	70.9	13.31	Yang et al., 2016
1944.9	175.9	24.78	Yang et al., 2018
506.4	45.8	36.07	Rode, 2021
156.9	15.9	13.02	This study

578

579 In the case of the two whole-cell systems (Yang et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2018), the E-
 580 factor increases from a 156.9 value obtained in this study to 782.7 and 1944.9;
 581 corresponding to 5.0- and 12.4-fold increase in waste generation, highlighting that the
 582 yield of the process has a lot of impact in this kind of metrics. Moreover, through the
 583 present work, GWP_{mass} is lowered 4.5- and 11.0-fold (70.9 and 175.9 vs. 15.9 kg CO₂-
 584 eq·kg⁻¹_{FDCA}) indicating again that final titers values have a substantial effect on these
 585 environmental performance indicators. In terms of GWP_{energy}, the value obtained remains
 586 nearly the same in both studies (13.02 vs. 13.31 and 24,78 kg CO₂-eq·kg⁻¹_{FDCA}),

587 indicating that the major sustainability gains arise from conversion and substrate loading,
588 even using higher reaction temperatures.

589 Finally, compared with the patented biotransformation route using resting cells of
590 *Klebsiella oxytoca* (Rode, 2021), a process which had previously reported the highest titer
591 to date, at 1.97 g/L, the enzymatic process in the present study still achieves a 3.2-fold
592 reduction in E-factor and a 2.9-fold and 2.8-fold decrease in GWP_{mass} and GWP_{energy} ,
593 respectively. This highlights the benefit of intensifying biocatalytic systems directly on
594 crude HMF streams.

595 It should be noted that these comparisons only cover the reaction (upstream) stage, as
596 downstream operations could not be consistently evaluated due to the lack of harmonized
597 data, and thus the overall environmental advantage of the present process is likely
598 underestimated.

599

600 4. CONCLUSION

601 This work demonstrates the enzymatic production of FDCA from lignocellulosic-derived
602 HMF as a sustainable strategy aligned with circular economy principles. The fusion of
603 8BxHMFO with CBM3 enabled one-step purification and immobilization on
604 microcrystalline cellulose, resulting in high immobilization yields and improved stability.
605 The immobilized enzyme showed optimal performance at 50 mM HMF, producing 7.2
606 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ FDCA with nearly complete yield. Importantly, the system efficiently converted
607 crude HMF, achieving 98.7% conversion and 70.6% yield, outperforming whole-cell
608 systems that generally exhibit lower titers and longer reaction times. This highlights the
609 robustness of the process against impurities present in lignocellulosic hydrolysates and
610 confirms its relevance under biorefinery conditions. Downstream recovery provided 88%

611 FDCA purity using ethanol as a green solvent, reinforcing the environmental value of the
612 approach. Overall, these findings, along with the evaluation of sustainable metrics,
613 validate biocatalysis as a sustainable and scalable route for FDCA production from
614 minimally processed substrates, paving the way for future industrial applications.

615 DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI AND AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES IN 616 THE WRITING PROCESS.

617 During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT (OpenAI, San Francisco,
618 USA) in order to improve the readability and clarity of the manuscript. After using this
619 tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility
620 for the content of the published article.

621

622 DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

623 The data supporting this study are openly available in the CORA repository at
624 <https://dataverse.csuc.cat/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.34810/data2637>

625

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